

FACTORS INFLUENCING THE DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS' CREATIVITY IN THE COURSE OF PENCIL DRAWING

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Abstract. *The given article discusses the importance of pencil drawing courses in the development of creativity in future visual arts teachers, methods of teaching the most convenient ways to learn drawing, how to further enhance creativity while teaching drawing, and the theoretical principles that should be followed during the drawing process in pencil art.*

Keywords: *pencil drawing, line, shadow, contour line, visual art, drawing, perspective, plastic anatomy, object, light and shadow, artificial and natural.*

“Pencil drawing is always a guiding pole and compass for us and in the ocean of different colors, it is the factor that saves those, who are sinking.”

Shari Lebren

It is important to suggest that visual art is a vast field for young creative students who aspire to master this area. Mastering drawing is essential in all forms of art. Therefore, knowledge of pencil drawing contributes to success in all forms of visual activity and ensures mastery. The desire to draw various pictures and use them in one's spiritual life has been a constant throughout history. As a result, specialists in this field have developed certain rules and principles of drawing, which have been improved over years and centuries.

By emphasizing the importance of enhancing students' skills in visual art, it is essential for future visual arts specialists to remember the ideas of famous representatives of the field and take them as their motto in their work. As the famous Russian artist and pedagogue D.N. Kardovskiy stated, "Mastering pencil drawing skills is the key to creating a unique color drawing work."

Definitely, the development of the ability to accurately depict objects in drawing is one of the main requirements in teaching pencil drawing.

Moreover, improving the ability of students to depict an object as realistically as possible from all sides is one of the most important aspects of pencil drawing education. For this, students must learn how to properly position the image on the paper, determine proportions accurately, and identify the correct placement of objects in space and their perspective relationships. To achieve the desired result, it is necessary to continually improve their knowledge, experience, and skills. Knowledge is gained through reading, studying, and reflection, while experience and skill are gained through continuous practice, effort, and perseverance. Another important condition for

learning is that each depicted object, event, or scene must be drawn based on direct observation, i.e., from nature.

However, the main goal of pencil drawing is to develop the future artist's ability to feel the essence of the world and depict it vividly in their work, while also conveying comprehensive knowledge about Uzbek and world art to the younger generation. In the field of visual arts, the process of forming practical skills is carried out through exercises in life-like representations of nature.

In order to accurately depict a shape, the student must first clearly imagine and learn to visualize its distinctive features. For a young and beginner artist, this is not an easy task and requires continuous theoretical and practical training. According to famous artists, if an artist stops drawing for a day, they fall back two days. Therefore, a young artist should never stop drawing from nature, as practicing accurate depictions of objects every day is crucial for their development.

At higher education institutions, while teaching future visual arts educators, it is of great importance not only to teach the practical aspects of pencil drawing but also to thoroughly instruct its theoretical foundations. Therefore, it is crucial to conduct pencil drawing lessons based on certain subjects, such as technical drawing, perspective, and plastic anatomy. The most fundamental of these are perspective and plastic anatomy. Without studying these subjects, it is difficult for students to complete even the simplest tasks correctly. Without understanding the principles of perspective, they cannot accurately determine the spatial position of an object, and without knowledge of plastic anatomy, they cannot draw human form or portraits. If a student does not have a solid understanding of the laws of light and shadow, they will not be able to accurately depict the color, size, and material characteristics of the object being depicted.

What is more important, the art of creating works of pencil drawing, like other technical subjects, primarily enables the artist to deeply analyze the shape, position, and composition of the depicted object, including the sources of light and shadow (both artificial and natural), and to create the image using various drawing tools.

The more complex the shape of the depicted object is, the more the artist must study and analyze it. A scientific approach to pencil drawing, especially when determining the linear and constructive structure of the object and its perspective position, is of great importance. Achieving a high level of proficiency in pencil drawing, as mentioned earlier, largely depends on the artist's ability to draw based on the object itself. Without mastering the skill of drawing from nature, one cannot achieve artistic development or become a highly skilled expert in their field.

Certainly, the skill of a student who has reached a high level of proficiency is shown in their ability to draw freely and expressively. This can be achieved through regular and active creative work with clearly defined goals. In the early stages of drawing, helping students develop the skill of drawing quickly and efficiently will contribute to improving their skills and enhancing their creativity. Therefore, if students are spending a lot of time in academic drawing classes, it is important to encourage them to practice specific exercises during independent hours or additional drawing lessons at home. The academic drawing process in educational settings plays a crucial role in building a strong foundation for students' creative skills and nurturing their artistic abilities. In this regard, it is necessary to focus students' attention on another important aspect during pencil drawing lessons.

Definitely, they must analyze the individual stages of the work, apply the correct technique during the drawing process, make adjustments as needed, and ensure that the drawing becomes clearer and more expressive as the process progresses.

Mastering the methodological sequence of drawing allows students to work with confidence, knowing exactly how each stage should be completed. A young artist with practical experience in drawing begins to develop the ability to foresee the final result. However, this ability to anticipate the outcome cannot be achieved independently by everyone; it comes through the guidance of a teacher and by gradually mastering the entire drawing process step by step.

By summarizing it is important to suggest that the importance for future visual arts educators to develop creative skills by gradually increasing the level of knowledge and abilities at each stage. This step-by-step approach to improving skills and techniques plays a vital role in their development as competent and creative art teachers.

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